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Failure Process Analysis of Robustness of Multi-layer Interdependent Networks

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ABSTRACT

Interdependent networks have become a hot research direction in the field of complex networks in recent years. At present, the research of interdependent networks mainly focuses on interdependent networks composed of two sub-networks, but complex systems in the real world may be composed of multiple sub-networks. This paper constructs a multi-dependent network model, studies its node failure mechanism and robustness issues, and conducts theoretical analysis of the robustness of three typical network combinations (non-ring structure, ring structure and mesh structure). The research results show that the robustness of the multi-layer interdependent network is related to the coupling strength between sub-networks, the average degree of external connections, the average degree of internal connections, and the number of sub-network nodes, and the performance of the characteristics is closely related to the network structure.

INTRODUCTION

After decades of development, the theoretical system of complex network research has been gradually established and improved, but these theories still have certain limitations. Most of the current research focuses on the cascading failures of a single network, but most real systems do not exist in isolation in real life. The normal operation of nodes in one system may be interdependent with some nodes in other systems, and its failures may cause other nodes to fail to operate normally, which may lead to large-scale cascading failures problems. A typical case is the Italian blackout that occurred on September 28, 2003. Due to the close coupling between the power network and the communication support network, the collapse of a power station caused a large number of nodes in the data acquisition and monitoring communication network to fail, causing more power plant failures, which in turn led to large-scale power outages. For such a coupled network in which the power network and the communication network have mutual dependencies, it is called interdependent network.

The research on the robustness of interdependent network is a new hotspot in the research of complex networks in recent years. Many scholars at home and abroad have applied this model to the structural modeling and robustness research of power networks, communication networks and transportation networks. Buldyrev, S.V., et al. (2010) first proposed a theoretical framework for the problem of cascading failures of interdependent network under random failures of nodes, which opened a new direction for the study of cascading failures in interdependent network. In order to study the influence of coupling probability on interdependent network, Parshani R., et al. (2010) proposed a set of classical theoretical methods. Cheng, Z.S., et al. (2015) studied the effects of different

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coupling modes between interdependent network on network cascading failures. Rahnamay N.M., et al. (2016) proposed a new interdependent Markov chain framework, which can extract the dependence relationship between two critical infrastructures, and then predict the resilience of cascading failures, and describe the dependence of the relationship on system reliability. influences. Wang, F., et al. (2018) analyzed the cascading failures problem of interdependent weighted networks based on seepage theory and local weighted traffic redistribution rules. Gao, Y.L., et al. (2017) analyzed the cascading failures and robustness of four interdependent network under different coupling modes under six different attack strategies. At present, scholars in various fields have done different levels of research on the problem of cascading network failures Goodrum, C.J., et al. (2018), Manish, T., et al. (2019), Malgorzata, T., et al (2019), Shen, A.W., et al.(2017), Hassan, H.A., et al. (2019), Qian, Y., et al. (2015).

CONSTRUCTION OF MULTI-LAYER INTERDEPENDENT NETWORK MODEL

At present, research on interdependent networks has mainly studied the robustness problem of two sub-networks. However, complex systems studied in reality may be composed of multiple sub-networks, that is, multi-layer interdependent networks (NON). In the modeling research of multiple dependent networks, we consider each node as a sub-network, and each edge as the interdependence between the sub-networks. Each sub-network i in the multi-network is defined as $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, and the number of nodes corresponding to each sub-network is N_i . At the same time, the internal nodes of each sub-network will be randomly connected with edges, and their degree distributions are respectively $P_i(k)$, where k is the node degree of the sub-network i . For any two sub-networks i and j , each node in the network i has at most a coupling interdependent edge with one node in the network j , and the Probability of connection is $q_{i,j}$; vice versa. Similar to the interdependent network composed of two sub-networks, if a node of a sub-network in a multilayer network system fails, the nodes in other sub-networks i that have a dependency relationship with it will also fail.

Literature Wang, K., et al. (2011) proposed three methods of multi-layer dependent networks, namely tree, star and ring multi-layer networks, as shown in Figure 1. In this paper, analytical expressions are proposed to study the probability of the maximum connected subgroups remaining in the n-layer network after cascade failure. For example, for a tree-like and star-like multi-layer interdependent network system, the probability of the largest connected subgroup after the cascade failure is $P_\infty = p[1 - \exp(-kP_\infty)]^n$. Where n is the number of sub-networks in the multi-layer interdependent network system and k is the average degree of the network. For a ring network, the maximum probability of connecting subgroups after cascading failure is $P_\infty = p(1 - e^{-kP_\infty})(qP_\infty - q + 1)$.

Figure 1. Three ways of multi-layer dependent networks

In studying the robustness of multi-layer network systems, we continue to assume that some nodes in the sub-network i with a proportion p_i will be attacked or removed from the entire network system, or that the nodes with a proportion r_i will be retained. This assumption will directly lead to the occurrence of a wider range of cascading failures: a proportion r_i of nodes in the network i will be removed, and then nodes that are not part of the huge component in the network will all fail; then these failed nodes in the network i will cause the nodes in other sub-networks with interdependent edges to fail, and the failure of these nodes will cause extensive failures in their sub-networks.

The purpose of studying the robustness of multi-layer network systems is to determine the number of remaining nodes in each sub-network at the end of the entire network cascade under different removal ratios p_i and different coupling dependency ratios $q_{i,j}$.

Suppose that the multilayer network system we are studying has n unknowns x_i . For the sub-network i , x_i represents the number of nodes remaining in this sub-network after the first step of cascading failure. Our criterion for judging the final state of a multilayer network system is somewhat similar to the Kirchhoff equation describing a resistance network details as follows:

Assume that the multilayer network system we are studying has unknowns. For a sub-network, it represents the number of nodes remaining in this sub-network after the first step of cascading failure. The first step of this cascading failure includes the nodes that were originally removed from the sub-network and the nodes that failed due to the existence of the coupling dependent edges.

Due to the different time periods of node failure, when considering the second step of cascading failure, consider the failure of nodes that do not belong to the huge component. For unknowns x_i , it can be expressed by the following general framework:

$$x_i = (1 - p_i) \prod_{j=1}^K [q_{ij} y_{ij} g_j(x_j) - q_{ji} + 1] \quad (1)$$

Among them, K is the number of other sub-networks i that have interdependence with the sub-networks in the multi-layer network system. For any one of these interdependent sub-network j , due to the interdependence with other networks, some nodes will fail, and the number of nodes in the remaining part is

$$y_{ij} = \frac{x_i}{(1 - p_j) q_{ji} y_{ji} g_j(x_j) - q_{ji} + 1} \quad (2)$$

The structure of a multi-layer network system can generally be divided into two cases for research, namely, a non-cyclic structure, a cyclic structure, and a network structure, which will be studied separately below.

ROBUSTNESS ANALYSIS OF TYPICAL NETWORK COMBINATIONS

The multi-layer network system with non-cyclic structure referred to in this article mainly includes linear structure, star structure and tree structure. as shown in picture 2:

Figure 2. Three forms of non-cyclic structure NON network

First assume that the NON network contains several n ER random networks, and the average degree of each sub-network is respectively k_1, \dots, k_n . And for the coupling dependency between any two sub-networks is $q_{ij} = 1$, it is a completely interdependent network. At the initial moment, remove the proportion P of nodes in the sub-network $i=1$, which can be obtained by formula (1) and formula (2):

$$f_i = \exp \left[-(1-p) \prod_{j=1}^n (1-f_j) \right], i=1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

The above formula has only a trivial solution $f_i = 1$ below $p > p_c$, where p_c is the percolation threshold. When each sub-network in the NON network has the same average degree, that is $k_i = k (i=1, 2, \dots, n)$, can $f_c \equiv f_i(p_c)$ be satisfied by the above formula:

$$f_c = \exp \left[\frac{f_c - 1}{nf_c} \right] \quad (4)$$

The above expression can be expressed as a Lambert function $W_-(x)$, that is

$$f_c = - \left[nW_- \left(-\frac{1}{n} e^{-\frac{1}{n}} \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (5)$$

Where $W_-(x)$ is the negative root of the two real roots of the Lambert function $W(x) \exp[W(x)] = x$.

When f_c is known, we can calculate the percolation threshold p_c and the magnitude of the huge component at this time.

$$\begin{cases} 1 - p_c = \left[nkf_c(1 - f_c)^{n-1} \right]^{-1} \\ P_\infty(p_c) = \frac{1 - f_c}{nkf_c} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

It is worth noting that the above formula is an expression that is generalized based on the results of some existing studies. For example, for the number of neutron networks in the above formula, that is, the cascading failure of a single complex network is similar to formula (4), $p_c = 1 - 1/k$. At this time, the final state $P_\infty(p_c) = 0$ of the network is consistent with the continuous second-order phase transition process. For the above formula $n=2$, we can obtain the results of the interdependent network consisting of two ER random networks. The results obtained are similar to those of Buldyrev et al., That is, a continuous first-order phase transition process. Therefore, based on formulas (2) and (3), we can get the exact expression of the order parameter $P_\infty(p_c)$, that is, the size of its huge component:

$$P_\infty = (1-p)[1 - \exp(-kP_\infty)]^n \quad (7)$$

Further analysis shows that the seepage threshold p_c of formula (6) is a functional relationship related to the number of sub-networks, the average degree k of the sub-networks, and so on. It can be

seen that the larger the number n of sub-networks, or the smaller the average degree k , the smaller the seepage threshold p_c and the more fragile the network. If the number of fixed sub-networks is n , when the average degree k is less than the required minimum $k < k_{\min}(n)$, $p_c \leq 0$. This means that when the average degree is less than the required minimum value, even if one node in the NON network is removed, it will cause the entire network to completely collapse. The minimum value required for the average degree of the NON network can be calculated using the following formula:

$$k_{\min}(n) = [nf_c(1-f_c)^{n-1}]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

Research shows that for the number of sub-networks $n=2$, the minimum required average degree $k_{\min}(2) = 2.4554$; for the number of sub-networks $n=1$, the minimum required average degree $k_{\min}(1) = 1$. In addition, the above formulas are common to several forms of acyclic structures.

RR network (Random Regular Network) refers to a random network with the same degree of each node. Now suppose the degree of each node in the network is k . For the above formulas (2) and (3), a new variable $r = f^{\frac{1}{k-1}}$ can be introduced. The k equations in the formula can be simplified into one equation, as shown below:

$$r = (r^{k-1} - 1)(1-p)(1-r^k)^{n-1} + 1 \quad (9)$$

For any removal ratio p , formula (9) can find a certain solution. Therefore, the critical removal ratio point and the final state after cascading failure can be obtained

$$1 - p_c = \frac{r-1}{(r^{k-1} - 1)(1-r^k)^{n-1}} \quad (10)$$

$$P_{\infty} = (1-p) \left(1 - \left\{ (1-p)^{\frac{1}{n}} P_{\infty}^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \left[1 - \left(\frac{P_{\infty}}{1-p} \right) - 1 \right] + 1 \right\}^k \right)^n \quad (11)$$

Comparing the above derivation results with the acyclic structure composed of the ER random network, we find that the acyclic structure composed of the RR network is more robust under the same average degree k . In an acyclic structure composed of ER random networks, there is a minimum average degree k_{\min} that changes with the size of the network n , while RR networks do not have such parameters. For an arbitrary average degree $k > 2$, the RR network is able to maintain stability by itself, that is, the critical removal of proportional nodes $p_c > 0$.

Ring structure

This paper assumes that a ring-shaped multilayer network composed of n ER networks has no direction, and the dependent coupling edges have no feedback. The ring structure is shown in Figure 4:

Figure 3. Two forms of NON network with ring structure

Assume that the removal ratio of each sub-network during the initial attack is P , the average degree of each sub-network $k_i = k$, and the coupling ratio between the networks $q_i = q$, which can be obtained from formulas (2) and (3):

$$P_\infty = (1-p)(1-e^{-kP_\infty})(qP_\infty - q + 1) \quad (12)$$

According to the above formula, when the coupling ratio $q_i = q = 1$ between the sub-networks, that is, when the interdependent network is a fully coupled network, if the removal ratio is very low, $P_\infty \rightarrow 0$, that is, the failure of a single node of the network will also cause the collapse of the entire network ;

When the coupling ratio $q_i = q = 0$ between the networks, the interdependent network will transform into a single complex network.

From the theoretical analysis of the above-mentioned ring structure, it is possible to draw a meaningful conclusion, that is, the size of the giant component and the percolation threshold P_c are related to the coupling strength q , the average degree k of external connections, and the average degree m of internal connections, and are The number of sub-networks n is irrelevant.

Network Structure

In addition to the ring structure and the non-ring structure, a multilayer network system may also have a network structure, as shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4. Two forms of network structure NON network

Due to the variety of network structure structures, there are two simplifying assumptions in the network structure analyzed in this article. (1) Assume that each sub-network has a coupling dependency with the same number of other sub-networks. As shown in Figures 5 (a) and (b), it means that there is a coupling dependency between each sub-network and 4 sub-networks. (2) Assume that each node between sub-networks has a coupling dependency relationship with probability q .

Now, an initial attack is performed on a multi-layer system of a network structure composed of an ER network. When the removal ratio of each sub-network is P , the final state equation of the network after the cascade failure occurs is:

$$P_{\infty} = \frac{1-P}{2^m} (1 - e^{-kP_{\infty}}) [1 - q + \sqrt{(1-q)^2 + 4qP_{\infty}}]^m \quad (13)$$

When $m=0$ or $q=0$ in the above formula, the above network is reduced to a single network. Observing the above formulas (13) and (14), we can get some differences in the robustness of the multi-layer system of the network structure composed of RR network and ER network:

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 - \left[1 - \frac{P_{\infty}}{(1-p)q(1-q-qP_{\infty})} \right]^{\frac{1}{k}} \\ &= 1 - p \left\{ 1 - \left[1 - \frac{P_{\infty}}{(1-p)q(1-q-qP_{\infty})} \right]^{\frac{k-1}{k}} \right\} (1-q+qP_{\infty})^m \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

When or in the above formula, the above network is reduced to a single network. Observing the above formulas (13) and (14), we can get some differences in the robustness of the multi-layer system of the network structure composed of RR network and ER network:

(1) When the coupling ratio $q < q_c$ in each sub-network represents weak coupling, the seepage shows a continuous second-order phase transition, and the phase transition point is P_c^{II} . and,

$$P_c^{\text{II}} = 1 - \frac{1}{k(1-q)^m} \quad (15)$$

(2) When the coupling ratio $q_c < q < q_{\max}$ in each sub-network represents weak coupling, percolation shows a continuous first-order phase transition, and the phase transition point is P_c^{I} .

(3) When the coupling ratio $q > q_{\max}$ in each sub-network represents weak coupling, which represents super coupling, removing any node in the network will cause the entire network to collapse.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to study the robustness of multi-layer dependent networks, this paper constructs a multi-layer interdependent network model and analyzes the robustness of typical network combinations.

The research shows that the robustness of the multilayer network system composed of RR network and ER network is different from that of ring and non-ring networks:

(1) When the coupling ratio $q < q_c$ in each sub-network represents weak coupling, the seepage shows a continuous second-order phase transition, and the phase transition point is P_c^{II} . and,

(2) When the coupling ratio $q_c < q < q_{\max}$ in each sub-network represents weak coupling, percolation shows a continuous first-order phase transition, and the phase transition point is P_c^{I} .

(3) When the coupling ratio $q > q_{\max}$ in each sub-network represents weak coupling, which represents super coupling, removing any node in the network will cause the entire network to collapse.

REFERENCES

- Buldyrev, S.V., Parshani, R., Paul, G., et al. (2010) Catastrophic cascade of failures in interdependent networks. *Nature*, 464: 1025-1028.
- Cheng, Z.S., Cao, J.D. (2015) Cascade of failures in interdependent networks coupled by different type networks. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 430: 193-220.
- Gao, Y.L., Chen, S.M., Nie, S., et al. (2017) Robustness analysis of interdependent networks under multiple-attacking strategies. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 496: 495-504.
- Goodrum et.al., 2018, Manish et al., 2019, Malgorzata et.al., 2019 C.J., Shields, C.P.F., Singer, D.J. (2018) Understanding cascading failures through a vulnerability analysis of interdependent ship-centric distributed systems using networks. *Ocean Engineering*, 150: 36-47.
- Hassan, H.A., Mohamad, E.H.G., Takawira, C.N. (2019) A Survey on Power System Blackout and Cascading Events: Research Motivations and Challenges. *Energies*, 12: 682.
- Malgorzata, T., Keith, B., Martin, R., et al. (2019) Cascading failures in scale-free interdependent networks. *Physical Review E*, 99: 032308.
- Manish, T., Espejo, U., Evangelos, P. (2019) Measuring network reliability and repairability against cascading failures. *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*, 52: 573-594.
- Parshani, R., Buldyrev, S.V., Havlin, S. (2010) Interdependent Networks: Reducing the Coupling Strength Leads to a Change from a First to Second Order Percolation Transition. *Physical Review Letters*, 105: 048701.
- Qian, Y., Wang, B, Xue, Y, et al. (2015) A simulation of the cascading failures of a complex network model by considering the characteristics of road traffic conditions. *Nonlinear Dynamics*, 80: 413-420.
- Rahnamay-Naeini, M., Hayat, M. (2016) Cascading Failures in Interdependent Infrastructures: An Interdependent Markov-Chain Approach. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, 7: 1997-2006.
- Shen, A.W., Guo, J.L., Wang, Z.J. (2017) Research on Methods for Improving Robustness of Cascading Failures of Interdependent Networks. *Wireless Personal Communications*, 95: 2111-2126.
- Wang, K., Zhang, B., Zhang, H.Z., Yin X.G., Wang, B. (2011) An electrical betweenness approach for vulnerability assessment of power grids considering the capacity of generators and load. *Physica A*, 390: 4692-4701.
- Wang, F., Tian, L.X., Du, R.J., et al. (2018) The robustness of interdependent weighted networks. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 508: 675-680.